

Caring during crisis: navigating risk and uncertainty in health, care and beyond

SoRU

Program Midterm Conference 2025
European Sociological Association
Research Network 22
Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty

SoRU

Colophon

Caring during crisis: navigating risk and uncertainty in health, care and beyond

Program Midterm Conference 2025 ESA RN22

Publisher

Marketing & Communicatie ESHPM

Design

PanArt.nl

Table of Contents

Welcome	p. 4
Program Overview	p. 5
Keynotes	p. 6
Sessions Overview	p. 8
Sessions Abstracts	p. 12
Session 1	p. 13
Session 2	p. 19
Session 3	p. 25
Session 4	p. 29
Practical Information	p. 35

Welcome

Dear participants of the Midterm Conference of the European Sociological Association Research Network 22 (RN22) *Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*, kindly hosted by Erasmus School of Health Policy & Management at the Erasmus University Rotterdam in the Netherlands,

This year marks the 20th anniversary of our network, a milestone that invites reflection on two decades of pioneering sociological inquiry into the dynamics of risk and uncertainty in modern societies. Since its inception, RN22 has provided a platform for scholars to examine the ways risks emerge, are communicated, and are managed across diverse societal domains. This anniversary is not only a moment to celebrate past achievements but also an opportunity to envision the future of risk sociology. As contemporary crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, climate emergencies, and geopolitical conflicts challenge established paradigms, RN22 remains committed to addressing these issues through innovative research and interdisciplinary collaboration.

At the Midterm Conference 2025 we aim to bring together both seasoned scholars and emerging voices to reflect on the network's legacy and to chart new directions for the study of risk and uncertainty. This year's theme *Caring during crisis* delves into the intersection of health, care, and crisis within the framework of risk sociology. Health and care systems are increasingly tested by cascading crises such as global pandemics, climate change, geopolitical instability, and socio-economic inequality. By foregrounding this theme we aim to foster a deeper understanding of how risk sociology can inform policies and practices that enhance practices of care during crisis and promote equitable health outcomes.

We are looking forward to an informal and engaging event, with a diverse set of participants from all corners of Europe and beyond, fascinating key-notes and an inspiring Risk Tour. Welcome in Rotterdam!

Kind regards,

Bert de Graaff & Veronica Moretti, coordinators of ESA RN22, and Karin van Vuuren, Roland Bal and Patricia van Loo-Kemp, local organizing committee.

Program Overview

Date & Time	Activity	Location (building, room)
Tuesday 28/10: PhD Workshop		
10:00 – 17:00	Closed session	Bayle, J7-43/45
Wednesday 29/10: Midterm Conference Day 1		
09:00 – 09:30	Registration / Coffee	Theil, C2-1
09:30 – 09:45	Opening ESHPM Dean Maarten IJzerman	Theil, C2-1
09:45 – 10:45	Keynote 1: Jens Zinn	Theil, C2-1
10:45 – 11:00	Short break	Theil, C2-1
11:00 – 12:30	Sessions 1 (exact program see below)	Theil, C2-1, C2-3; C2-4
12:30 – 13:00	Lunch	Theil, C2-1
13:00 – 14:30	Sessions 2 (exact program see below)	Theil, C2-1, C2-3; C2-4
14:30 – 14:35	Short break	Theil, C2-1
14:35 – 15:30	Keynote 2: Patrick Brown	Theil, C2-1
15:30 – 18:30	Risk Tour	City center
18:30 – 19:00	No program	
19:00 – 22:00	Conference Dinner	Vessel 11
Thursday 30/10: Midterm Conference Day 2		
09:30 – 10:00	Registration / Coffee	Theil, C2-1
10:00 – 11:00	Keynote 3: Roland Bal	Theil, C2-1
11:00 – 11:15	Short break	Theil, C2-1
11:15 – 12:45	Sessions 3 (exact program see below)	Theil, C2-1, C2-3; C2-4
12:45 – 13:45	Lunch	Theil, C2-1
13:45 – 15:15	Sessions 4 (exact program see below)	Theil, C2-1, C2-3; C2-4
15:15 – 15:30	Short break	Theil, C2-1
15:30 – 16:30	Keynote 4: Marion Koopmans	Theil, C2-1
16:30 – 17:00	Closing and wrap-up	Theil, C2-1

Session 2.3: Visualising Risk and (Mis)Communication in Crisis (1)

29/10 13:00 – 14:30, Theil C2-4, Chair: Roland Bal

Annalisa Plava, University of Bologna: Caring with...the (comic) strips. Navigating the datafication of health and risks of online identity theft. Email: annalisa.plava2@unibo.it

Contemporary risks due to the datafication of health take on new characteristics and their effects are potentially unlimited. Cyberattacks on healthcare are on the rise by 74% worldwide with an average of 209 attempts per day. As user-patients we directly generate this data and consent to the storage by health professionals by interpreting the online as a prosthesis of the offline. Data monitors us in our extimacy and intimacy. Monitoring the health stare by sharing our medical data with professionals and related tools, therefore, is a risk we assume even if not always aware of it. However, this personal information could be compromised or misused and impact on new forms of victimization as the Online Identity Theft (OIDT). European OIDT victims often do not report the crime, believing that the harm suffered is not significant enough or, as in the health data victims, lacking adequate resources to counteract it. With the aim of expanding awareness to prevent OIDT but also to support the victims, an interdisciplinary team (sociologists, IT experts and an artist) realized a graphic project introducing Secure and Care Comics. The narrations, practical information and emotional dynamics have been outlined by 23 semi-structured interviews with OIDT experts and 47 structured interviews with victims. Key informants' perspectives were the starting point to craft the storyboard and realize comic strips. In this scenario, comic strips which merge social research, technical insights, and art, were developed to 1) raise awareness of the risks related to health data 2) inform patient-users, victims, and health professionals about the social risks of OIDT 3) encourage health institutions to activate effective support systems to preserve patient data.

Aistė Balžekienė, Kaunas University of Technology: Risk Perception, Trust and Societal resilience in Turbulent Times: Navigating Uncertainties in Lithuania. Email: aiste.balzekiene@ktu.lt

During recent years societies are facing non-closing circle of crises, with multiple overlaying risks and uncertainties. Lithuania witnesses on the highest inflation in Europe, was severely affected by the energy crisis and is in constant uncertainty around military threats. The concept of polycrisis is becoming an important analytical lens to explore the amplification and overlaying effects of different crises and risks. There has been increasing emphasis in public discourse on the societal resilience and factors behind it. The societal resilience in polycrisis situations and contexts besides institutional capacities in crises response should include local knowledge, empower leadership of communities and NGO's, and strengthen social networks for disaster preparedness.

This presentation is exploring how risk perception of complex risks and trust in institutions are shaping the perception societal resilience for extreme situations in Lithuania. Presentation is based on the data from representative public opinion survey with 1003 respondents, conducted in October 2024, in Lithuania. Predictors of societal resilience include trust in institutions and communities; risk perception and intersecting demographic characteristics. Results of the survey indicate the low trust in government, municipalities as well as NGO's and their abilities effectively to respond in crisis situations. Trust in army, police and first responders is much higher. Societal resilience is also related to the historical memory of past crises and optimistic attitudes towards the future.

This presentation is based on the project „Socio-spatial determinants of societal vulnerability and resilience to crises and strengthening the crisis response potential of communities” (SERENITY), funded by the Research council of Lithuania, no. Nr. S-VIS-23-21.